

Ecoenzyme Production from Telang Flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) Flower Extract as an Antioxidant for Acne

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Face skin is one of the things that is of concern to the public. Where facial health itself is something that can increase a person's self-confidence. However, basically everyone has different skin conditions and problems. These problems include acne, dull skin, black spots, and even fine lines. This has triggered many people to be interested in skin care and are even willing to pay high costs. Maybe for people who already have an income, going to a beauty clinic for skin care has become commonplace and its included in the list of monthly needs. This is different from teenagers who are still students or college students who are more interested in things that are low budget but have good benefits because they have to save expenses and prioritize academic needs over tertiary needs. Indonesia has a variety of plants that are considered useful as medicines and cosmetic ingredients. One of them is the *Telang* flower or *Clitoria ternatea* (scientific name). I support this theme because the *Telang* flower is a flower that has many benefits, especially for beauty, then the *Telang* flower itself is not a species that is difficult to obtain, and can be an alternative for reducing skin problems with natural ingredients without side effects.

The role of plant extracts on the skin is mainly associated with antioxidant activity, especially for its powerful antioxidant triterpenes, saponins, and flavonoids (Mabberley, 2008), skin rejuvenation (Batubara *et al.*, 2010), skin brightening (Olumide, 2010), and photoprotection (Pouillot *et al.*, 2011); (Nitalikar *et al.*, 2010). Butterfly flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) contains good ingredients and is beneficial for the skin. *Telang* flower has several pharmacological potentials as antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-depressant, anthelmintic, anti-cancer and anti-diabetic (Nurmiati, 2022). *Telang* flowers contain tannins, flobatins, carbohydrates, saponins, triterpenoids, polyphenols, flavanol glycosides, proteins, alkaloids, anthraquinones, anthocyanins, 4-ene-3,6 dione stigmasite, volatile oils, and steroids (Chusak *et al.*, 2018). According to Adila and Agustien (2013), this content is also found in curcuma rhizomes which functions as an antimicrobial so it is often used in traditional medicinal ingredients. The secondary metabolite compounds produced by *Clitoria ternatea* can generally inhibit the growth of pathogens that are detrimental to human life, including the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, the fungus *Neurospora* sp, *Rhizopus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. Where the *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria is the bacteria that causes

acne (Sari *et al.*, 2013). The antioxidant content functions to ward off free radicals in the skin (Vidiyanti *et al.*, 2023). According to Wuryanti, (2009) in Yolanda (2021) states that the benefits of coenzymes in the health sector are to treat skin diseases on the feet in patients who have suffered from diabetes for decades and as an acne medication. Coenzyme fermentation products are effective as potential antimicrobials that can inhibit microbial growth (Rahmadani *et al.*, 2022).

Butterfly flower is one of the species that is easily found or marketed. Butterfly flower (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) is a vine that commonly grows in open areas along roads and slopes. Butterfly flower plants are naturally found in grasslands, open forests, bushes, riverbanks and other open places, and are vines on trees or yard fences (Nurmiati, 2022). Many farmers cultivate butterfly pea flowers (*Clitoria ternatea* L.). Even in urban areas there are people who cultivate butterfly pea flowers. Butterfly pea flowers can also be cultivated yourself because they are easy to care for and their growth period is very fast (Cook *et al.*, 2005). The butterfly pea flower comes from tropical Asia and is often found in Ternate and North Maluku. It is thought to originate from tropical Asia, but there are also those who believe it originated from central South America and spread to tropical regions in the 19th century, including Indonesia (Kosai *et al.*, 2015). The spread of this flower to tropical regions includes the continents of Asia, Australia and Africa. This causes the distribution of *Clitoria ternatea* L. to be widespread and easy to find in many places, especially in tropical regions (Shen *et al.*, 2016).

Clitoria ternatea is a source of herbal or natural treatment. Since the time of their ancestors, Indonesian people have known herbal plants to treat all kinds of diseases. One of the reasons why herbal medicines are the choice is because herbal medicines are more economical and have fewer side effects than modern medicines (Parwata, 2016). In this regard, herbal medicines are suitable for long-term use (Mierza *et al.*, 2023). The face is a sensitive part of the body compared to other body parts (Chentana *et al.*, 2012). So you can't use products on your face carelessly. To avoid side effects from chemicals, it is highly recommended to use herbal ingredients that do not cause side effects (Azis *et al.*, 2022). Many studies have proven that antioxidants can prevent cell damage and premature aging such as fine lines (Sadowska and Bartosz, 2014). Herbal care products are products formulated using various permitted cosmetic ingredients, where one or more herbal ingredients are used to provide certain cosmetic benefits. Herbal extract is an ancient methodology that has been found in Greek scriptures and the Vedas. It is processed by crushing the ingredients in a bowl and then squeezing them to obtain the juice. Herbal plants are generally defined as dead non-woody plants (Shivanand *et al.*, 2010). With the production of butterfly pea flower extract (*Clitoria ternatea*), antioxidants

can be consumed without any harmful side effects for the skin which has higher sensitivity than other parts of the body.

It can be concluded that the coenzyme extracted from butterfly pea flowers (*Clitoria ternatea*) has potential as a natural ingredient for skin care, one of which is anti-acne. The ingredients or compounds found in flowers can provide antioxidant benefits, inhibit the growth of acne-causing bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, and play a role in rejuvenating and brightening the skin naturally without any side effects because they come from quality herbal ingredients that are easily available.

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